

THE ELECTROCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF COLLOIDAL SILICIC ACID PART I INTERACTION WITH BASES.*

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The interaction of silicic acid sols with dilute and concentrated bases has been studied. A comparison of the free and total acidities (at the first inflexion point) of the sols and those of their ultrafiltrates shows that the sols behave as strong acids. Titration curves with different dilute bases [NaOH, Ba(OH)₂, Ca(OH)₂] show inflexion points (first inflexion point) indicating full neutralisation of an acid between p_H 4.5 and 5.6 [with NaOH between p_H 5.17 and 5.4; with Ba(OH)₂ between p_H 4.87 and 5.6 and with Ca(OH)₂ between p_H 4.5 and 5.5.] A comparison of the slopes of the titration curves shows that the intensities with which different bases react with the sol are in the order Ca(OH)₂ > Ba(OH)₂ > NaOH but the amount of acid neutralised by these bases at each of the inflexion points is the same. The potentiometric titration curves of the sol with concentrated solutions of NaOH show second inflexion points between p_H 11.0 and 11.70. The lower the silica content of the sol, the lower is the p_H at which the second inflexion occurs. The total acidity, expressed in normality per litre, calculated from the second inflexion point, shows fair agreement with the silica content of the sol expressed in g. mols. per litre. The evidence shows that the salt NaHSiO₃ is formed at the second inflexion point. The ultrafiltrates of different sols contain different amounts of dissolved silicic acid. The buffer capacity curves show only one maximum near about the point of half neutralisation. This maximum value is considerably greater than that of an acid in true solution.

This paper deals with some aspects of the interactions of silicic acid sols with bases which have not been covered by previous investigators on this subject. The potentiometric titration curves of a number of carefully purified silicic acid sols have been obtained and the features of the curves, that is, their slopes and buffer capacities in different p_H regions, examined.

The sols were prepared by the action of chemically pure hydrochloric acid on solutions of sodium silicate (Merck's pure quality and dialysed in parchment bags against repeated changes of distilled water till the dialysate gave no test for chloride with silver nitrate). The sols L' and P were then electro-dialysed for effecting further purification. The membranes were purified as described by Rabinowitsch and Kargin (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1935, 31, 289). The general experimental arrangements, the method of titration and the apparatus used were the same as those described in a previous paper from this laboratory (Mukherjee *et al.*, *Indian J. Agric. Sci.*,

* The results given in this paper have been taken from the annual reports (1936-37, 1937-38, 1938-39) submitted to the Imperial Council of Agricultural Research, India,

1936, 6, 517). It was considered desirable to check the initial p_H values obtained with the hydrogen electrode with those obtained with a different electrode, e.g., the glass electrode. A Morton type glass electrode in conjunction with a Cambridge valve potentiometer was used.

The Reproducibility of the E. M. F. of the Hydrogen Electrode.

It has been previously observed in this laboratory (Mukherjee *et. al.*, *loc. cit.*) that the initial p_H values of the sol, as measured from the E.M.F. of the hydrogen electrode show irregular variations. These variations, however, did not materially affect the nature of the titration curves or the total acidity values calculated from them. On cleansing and replatinising the electrodes more concordant p_H values were often obtained with this sol. The extent to which reproducible values of the p_H can be obtained has been examined. The electrodes were cleansed and replatinised each time before use. The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Sol.		p_H .						Average p_H .
K	Hydrogen electrode	4'14	4'05	4'02	3'92	3'90	4'00	4'00
	Glass electrode	3'96	3'97	4'00	4'02			3'99
L	Hydrogen electrode	4'47	4'45	4'44	4'46	4'44	4'43	4'45
			4'45	4'43				
	Glass electrode	4'45	4'40	4'40	4'50			4'44
L'	Hydrogen electrode	3'97	4'04	3'98	3'99			4'00
P	Hydrogen electrode	4'73	4'70	4'67	4'70	4'67		4'69

The good agreement between the initial p_H values of the sols measured with the hydrogen electrode on different days and between the average from the hydrogen electrode with that from the glass electrode indicate, that the hydrogen electrode is serviceable at such low unbuffered hydrogen ion concentration.

Interaction of Silicic Acid Sols with Dilute Bases.

The free and total acidities of silicic acid sols K, L', M, P and Q as well as of their ultrafiltrates are given in Table II (see also Figures 1, 2, 3). The

silica contents of the sols and the p_H at the inflexion points in the titration curves are also shown in the table.

FIG. 1.
Sol. L'.

Curves 1-2 refer respectively to Sols-
NaOH and Sol-Ca(OH)₂.

FIG. 2.
Sol. M.

Curves 3-5 refer respectively to
Sol-NaOH, Sol-Ba(OH)₂ and Sol-
Ca(OH)₂.

TABLE II.

Sol.	SiO ₂ per litre.	Free acidity (normality).	p_H at first inflexion.	Total acidity (normality).	Base used.
Sol K	0.33 g. mol.	10.00×10^{-5}	4.50	10.00×10^{-5}	Ca(OH) ₂
Ultrafiltrate of sol K	—	0.81	—	1.1	"
Sol L'	0.10	16.0	4.80	14.5	Ca(OH) ₂
Ultrafiltrate of sol L'	—	1.23	—	1.2	NaOH Ca(OH) ₂
Sol M	0.16	7.08	4.70	8.9	Ca(OH) ₂
			4.87	9.0	Ba(OH) ₂
			5.17	9.0	NaOH
Ultrafiltrate of sol M	—	0.68	—	0.75	Ba(OH) ₂
Sol P	0.026	2.0	5.5	3.8	Ca(OH) ₂
Ultrafiltrate of sol P	—	0.2	—	3.8	Ba(OH) ₂ Nil
Sol Q	0.26	7.9	4.84	14.5	Ca(OH) ₂
			4.96	14.5	Ba(OH) ₂
Ultrafiltrate of sol Q	—	0.89	—	1.2	"

A comparison of the total acidities of the sols and their ultrafiltrates shows beyond doubt that colloidal silicic acid possesses an intrinsic acid character independent of the presence of dissolved acids in the system. Sol P shows a very low total acid, compared to other sols. It is to be noted that the silica content of the sol is much lower than that of the other sols. This probably explains the very weakly acidic properties observed by Rabinowitsch and Kargin (*loc. cit.*) with sols having very low (0.02%) silica contents.

In agreement with previous observations from this laboratory (Mukherjee *et al*, *Trans. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1937, 1, 227), the titration curves show inflexion points in the acid region. An inspection of the curves of Rabinowitsch and Laskin (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1928, 134, 387) shows similar inflexion points in the acid region, between p_H 5.2 and 5.4. The occurrence of the inflexion point in the acid region indicates that the acid titrated may contain several dissolved acids having different dissociation constants and/or a polybasic acid. The negligible total acidity of the ultrafiltrate shows that the sol does not contain dissolved acid, other than silicic acid. If the sol behaved as a polybasic acid the titration curves may be expected to show further inflexion points at concentrations of the added base which are multiples of the total acid at the first inflexion point. The

FIG. 3.

Sol Q.

FIG. 4.

Sol E.

titration curves (*vide* curves 10, 12, 14, 16, 17) of silicic acid sols with concentrated alkali do not show a second inflexion point till a high p_H value, which lies between 11.7 and 11.0 depending on the concentration of silica in the sol, is reached; and it appears that the polybasic acid character, if any, is not evident within the range of p_H values used. The smooth nature of the curves (*vide* curves 11, 13 and 15) obtained by plotting buffer capacities against concentration of added alkali, supports this conclusion. The interaction of silicic acid sol with concentrated alkalis has been dealt with in a subsequent section (*vide* p. 589).

The potentiometric titration curves (*vide* curves 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8', 9') of the sols with $Ba(OH)_2$, $Ca(OH)_2$ and $NaOH$ show inflexion points when equal amounts of the bases have been added. The inflexion points in the titration curves with different bases, however, do not lie at the same p_H . The inflexion point in the titration curve with caustic soda lies at the highest p_H and that in the calcium hydroxide curve at the lowest. An examination of the slopes of the curves shows that the calcium hydroxide curve has a flatter run than the baryta curves. The slope of the latter curve is again smaller than that of the $NaOH$ curve. Thus the buffering effect and hence the intensity of the reaction is in the order: $Ca(OH)_2 > Ba(OH)_2 > NaOH$. The greater effect of calcium hydroxide compared to $Ba(OH)_2$ is in agreement with the greater insolubility of calcium silicate compared

FIG. 5.

Sol R

FIG. 6.

10, 11-Sol K; 10', 11' Theoretical.

to barium silicate noted by Joseph and Hancock (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2813). Alternatively the salt molecule formed on the surface under these conditions by interaction with calcium hydroxide are more insoluble or stable than those formed with baryta. In the next paper of this series it will be shown that in the interaction of silicic acid sols with barium and calcium chlorides, on the other hand, the barium salt has a greater effect in that it liberates a larger amount of acid. It thus appears that the resulting salt molecules have different properties in the acid and alkaline regions indicating two different types of reactions.

Previous results (Mukherjee *et. al.*, *loc. cit.*, 1937) show that the total acidity of a silicic acid sol, calculated from the first inflexion points in the titration curves with dilute bases, shows a fair agreement with that calculated from minima in the conductometric titration curves. This coincidence is characteristic of a strong acid. Moreover, it will be seen from the following table that the observed slope, $d\mu/dc$ (the rate of change of specific conductivity μ with concentration c of added bases) of the conductometric titration curves (*vide* curves 8, 9) do not differ widely in the initial part of the titration from the value calculated for the neutralisation of hydrochloric acid.

TABLE III.

Sol.	Base used.	$d\mu/dc$	
		Calculated.	Observed.
E	Ba(OH) ₂	0.326	0.330
F	„	„	0.263
R	NH ₄ OH	0.315	0.320

This observation is important in the light of a recent paper by Bruyn and Oberbeek (*Kolloid Z.*, 1938, 84, 816) who found that silver iodide sols contain foreign ions such as Cu⁺⁺ and Zn⁺⁺ coming from distilled water used for the purification by electro dialysis and electrode cantation. As a result they found that the potentiometric and conductometric titration curves indicate a perceptible buffer action which disappeared on using purer double distilled water. It will appear from the data cited above that no such disturbing foreign ions, Cu⁺⁺, Zn⁺⁺ or Al⁺⁺⁺ are present in the silicic acid sols used by us. The conductometric titration curves (*vide* curves 8, 9) show no such buffering in the initial stages of the titrations. Tests for Cu⁺⁺⁺ in the silicic acid sols by means of rubeanic acid in slightly ammoniacal medium also gave negative results.

*Interaction of Silicic Acid Sol with Alkali in
highly Alkaline Regions.*

Reference has already been made (*vide p. 586*) to the occurrence of inflexion points in the acid region with dilute bases. Sols K, L, L', P and Q have been titrated with concentrated solutions of caustic soda upto nearly p_H 12'0. Titration with baryta and calcium hydroxide is not possible on account of coagulation.

FIG. 7.

12, 13-Sol L : 12', 13'-Theoretical.

FIG. 8.

Sol L'.

The titration curves (10, 12, 14, 16, 17, 18) all show an inflexion point in the p_H region 11'0 to 11'70. The silica contents of the sols have been given in Table IV together with the p_H at the second inflexion.

TABLE IV

*Relation between silica content of the sol and the p_H of the
second inflexion.*

Sol	SiO ₂ per litre.	p_H at the second inflexion point.
K	0'33 g. mol.	11'65
L	0'27	11'70
Q	0'26	11'70
L'	0'10	11'45
P	0'027	11'05

Table IV shows that the p_H at the second inflexion diminishes with the silica content of the sol. Treadwell and Wieland (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1930, 13, 842) have also observed that the titration curves of sodium silicate solutions with hydrochloric acid show definite inflexion points near about p_H 11.0 and that this p_H varies with the concentration of the solution. The variation of the p_H at the second inflexion point with the silica content of the sol has been studied by titrating different dilutions of sol Q. The results are given below.

TABLE V.

Dilution.	SiO ₂ per litre.	p_H of the second inflexion.	Total acidity at inflexion (in normality).
Pure sol	0.26 g. mol.	11.70	0.26
1:2.5	0.10	11.55	0.10
1:4	0.065	11.35	0.06
1:10	0.026	11.00	0.027

It should, however, be mentioned that for small changes in the concentrations of the sols the change in the p_H of the second inflexion point is not appreciable (*vide* Table IV).

FIG. 9.

16-Sol Q; 16a-Q/2.5; 16b-Q/4; 16c-Q/10.

FIG. 10.

17-titration as usual
18 " in bottle.

Britton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 425) observed inflexion points between p_H 10.0 and 11.0 when silicic acid, freshly prepared by the interaction of sodium silicate solutions with hydrochloric acid, was titrated with baryta and calcium hydroxide. Treadwell and König (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1933, 16, 468) prepared silicic acid sol by electrodialysing a solution of sodium silicate and titrated with caustic soda solution to nearly p_H 13. Their titration curve shows an inflexion point at p_H 11.8 and in the alkaline region is almost similar to curves obtained in the present works. Differences are, however, to be observed in the acid region. The titration curve obtained by them shows a strong buffering between p_H 6.0 and 7.0. The curves (*vide* curves 10, 12, 14, 16, 17, 18) given in this paper do not show a buffer action in this region. A second point of difference is that the titration curve of Treadwell and König does not show the strong acid character of the sol in the initial stages of its titration with a dilute base which has been noted in this work, as also by Rabinowitsch and Laskin (*loc. cit.*). This arises probably from the fact that they used comparatively concentrated alkali (0.1N) from the beginning, whereas, 0.01N-alkali has been added in small drops in this work to get the first inflexion.

Relation between Silica Content of the Sol and the Total Acid Neutralised at the Second Inflexion.

In the following table the total acidities of the sols neutralised at the second inflexion have been compared with their silica contents, determined by analysis.

TABLE VI.

Sol.	Total acidity at inflexion point.	SiO ₂ per litre.
K	0.35 N	0.33 g. mol.
L	0.26	0.27
Q	0.26	0.26
L	0.10	0.10
P	0.026	0.027

It will be seen from Table IV that the total acidity values, calculated from inflexion points in the alkaline region, show fair agreement with the silica contents of the sols.

The titrations of silicic acid sols with concentrated alkalis already referred to were completed within the course of a single day. Fresh

additions of alkalis were made after the E.M.F. was found to remain constant for 15 minutes and a complete titration generally took about 11 hours. To ascertain whether equilibrium was fully attained at each stage during the titration, 20 c.c. of sols Q and T were taken in each of a number of Jena bottles with glass stoppers and increasing amounts of alkalis were added and the bottles frequently stirred. A long interval (48 hours for sol Q and 70 hours for sol T) was allowed for the interaction and the p_H values were determined with the hydrogen electrode. The results are shown in Fig. 10 and Table VII.

TABLE VII.

Sol.	SiO ₂ per litre.	p_H at second inflexion.	Total acidity at second inflexion.
Q (Titration as usual)	0.26 g. mol.	11.70	0.26N
Q (Titration in bottles)	„	11.55	0.265
T (Titration as usual)	0.17	11.47	0.17
T (Titration in bottles)	„	11.33	0.17

The total acidity values calculated from the second inflexion points are in close agreement with the silica content of the sols. The results also show that the time allowed for in the continuous titration curves is practically sufficient for the attainment of equilibrium.

The Composition of the System at the Inflexion Point at High p_H .

Table VIII shows the ratio Na₂O:SiO₂ of different sols at the inflexion points at highly alkaline region.

TABLE VIII.

Sol.	Na ₂ O: SiO ₂ at inflexion point.
K	1 : 1.88
L	1 : 2.07
L'	1 : 2.0
P	1 : 2.07
Q	1 : 2.0

Thus, at the inflexion points in the titration curves the values of the ratio $\text{Na}_2\text{O}:\text{SiO}_2$ do not appreciably differ from 1:2. This suggests that the composition of the system at the inflexion point may be either NaHSiO_3 or NaSi_2O_5 . The presence of only one maximum near about the point of half neutralisation in the buffer capacity curve (*vide* curves 11, 13, 15) shows definitely that the second inflexion point indicates only the first stage of neutralisation of the colloidal acid and that the composition of the system at this point is NaHSiO_3 . Treadwell and Wieland (*loc. cit.*) and Harman (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, 31, 611) in their electrometric titrations of solutions of sodium silicate of different concentrations obtained two inflexion points corresponding to the first and second stages of neutralisation of a dibasic acid. They concluded that the first inflexion points in the titration curves of solutions of sodium silicate with hydrochloric acid at about p_H 11.0 correspond to the formation of NaHSiO_3 .

A comparison of the slopes of the titration curves (curves 10, 12, 10' and 12') of the sols with those of hypothetical acids in true solution having corresponding total acidities and dissociation constant, calculated from the p_H at half neutralisation, shows that the inflexion points in the titration curves of the sols lie at a lower p_H than those in the case of acids in true solution and that at higher concentrations of added alkali the titration curve of the sol has a flatter run than that of the hypothetical acid. The stronger buffer action of the sol is due to its colloidal nature arising from the fact that a continuous solution of the colloidal particles takes place in this region. The particles thus act as a reservoir from which fresh quantities of the acid pass into true solution. The buffer capacities have been discussed in a subsequent section.

Dissociation Constant of Colloidal Silicic Acid.

The titration curves of silicic acid sols with concentrated NaOH resemble those of a weak monobasic acid in true solution. If we now assume that the whole of the silica in the sol is present in a state of true solution and that the molar concentration of silica present in the sol represents its total acidity, the dissociation constant of colloidal silicic acid can be calculated from given points in the titration curves according to Henderson's equation,

$$H = K \frac{a - b - H + OH}{b + H - OH} \quad \dots (1)$$

where 'a' represents the initial concentration of acid given by the molar concentration of silica in the sol; 'b', the concentration of added base; H, the hydrogen ion concentration calculated from given p_K in the titration curve and OH, the concentration of hydroxyl ions. The results obtained are given in the following table.

TABLE IX.

I	II	III	IV	V
K	0.33	11.0	9.28	9.0
L	0.27	11.12	9.28	9.0
Q	0.26	11.17	9.28	9.0
Q diluted 1 : 2.5	0.10	10.88	9.28	9.0
L	0.10	10.88	9.28	9.0
Q diluted 1 : 4	0.065	10.91	9.28	9.0
P	0.027	10.54	9.28	9.0
Q diluted 1 : 10	0.026	10.41	9.28	9.0

Column I gives the reference number of each sol, column II, their silica contents in g. mol. per litre, column III, the p_K values calculated at the points of half neutralisation, and column IV and V, the p_K values calculated at the points of half neutralisation of acids in true solution having dissociation constants respectively of 5.2×10^{-10} (*vide* p. 591) and 10^{-9} (Hägg, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1926, 155, 21) and the corresponding total acidities of the sols. The p_K values for dissolved silicic acid corresponding to this stage of neutralisation are given in Table IXA for comparison.

TABLE IXA.

Author.	First dissociation constant of silicic acid.	p_K .
Hägg (<i>loc. cit.</i>)	10^{-9}	9.0
Treadwell and Wieland (<i>loc. cit.</i>)	$10^{-9.7}$	9.7
Joseph and Oakley (<i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1925 127, 2813)	10^{-10}	10.0
Harman (<i>loc. cit.</i>)	4.2×10^{-10}	9.3

It appears that the p_K values calculated from the points of half neutralisation of the sols are not constant but have a tendency to decrease with decrease in the concentration of the sols. The values obtained in

the case of acids in true solution, on the other hand, are constant within the range of concentrations studied. This difference probably arises out of the assumption that the whole of the silica is present in a state of true solution. Also the p_x values calculated at the points of half neutralisation according to equation (1) are not in agreement with those found for dissolved silicic acid.

Assuming solid silicic acid to be in equilibrium with dissolved silicic acid and its ions and applying the law of mass action, its first dissociation constant can be calculated as follows :

$$[H^+].[HSiO_3^-] = K_1.[H_2SiO_3] = K_1S \quad \dots (2)$$

where S is the concentration of dissolved undissociated silicic acid molecules in equilibrium with the solid phase. Since

$$[H^+] + [B^+] = [OH^-] + [HSiO_3^-]$$

where B represents the concentration of Na we have

$$[HSiO_3^-] = [H^+] + [B^+] - [OH^-]$$

and

$$[H^+]\{[H^+] + [B^+] - [OH^-]\} = K_1S.$$

Thus K_1S can be calculated from the p_H at a given point in the titration curve and the amount of base added. The values of K_1S thus calculated at the second inflexion points of sols K, L, Q, T, L' and P are given in Table X.

TABLE X.

Sol.	Silica content per litre.	p_H at second inflexion.	K_1S .
K	0.33 g. mol.	11.65	7.57×10^{13}
L	0.27	11.70	4.93
Q	0.26	11.70	4.93
T	0.17	11.47	5.49
L'	0.10	11.45	3.28
P	0.027	11.05	2.05

K_1S should have a constant value if the solution were saturated with respect to an unequivocal solid phase. But it is found to decrease with a decrease in the concentration of the sol (except in the case of sol T).

The concentrations of dissolved silicic acid in the ultrafiltrates* of the sols were next determined using the method of Lucas and King (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 2385). The colour developed on adding ammonium molybdate and sulphuric acid to the ultrafiltrate was matched against a standard picric acid colour in a Hellige colorimeter. The results are given below.

TABLE XI.

Sol.	SiO ₂ per litre.	SiO ₂ in the ultrafiltrate per litre (at 30°) (S).	p_H of ultrafiltrate.	Calc. p_H of the ultra-filtrate.	p_H .
Q	0.26 g. mol.	8.3×10^{-4} g. mol.	5.05	† 6.04	‡ 6.19
T	0.17	9.8	4.80	6.00	6.15
L'	0.10	6.8	4.93	6.09	6.23
P	0.027	4.7	5.70	6.17	6.32

If silicic acid has a definite solubility§ the amount of silicic acid determined in the ultrafiltrates of the sols should have a constant value. The results, however, show that the ultrafiltrates of the sols contain different amounts of silicic acid and is not related in a simple way to concentration. The following factors require consideration.

* 'Finest' cella ultrafilters were used.

† Calculated on the assumption that the first dissociation constant of silicic acid is 10^{-9} , the effect of the second one being insignificant.

‡ Calculated on the assumption that the first dissociation constant of silicic acid is 5.2×10^{-10} (*vide* Table XII).

§ Widely different values for the solubility of silica are found in literature. The most systematic work on the solubility of silica carried out so far is that of Lenher and Merrill (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 39, 26, 30). They found that one litre of water dissolves 0.428 g. of SiO₂ at 90° and 0.16 g. at 25°. What they measured, however, was "the amount of silica which passed from a non-filtrable to a filtrable state." It was not definitely known whether this amount went into true solution or became colloidal hydrogel of silicic acid. The mean value of the solubility of colloidal silicic acid obtained in this work is 0.045 g. per litre, a value which is considerably less than that obtained by them.

(i) Varying amounts of sodium silicate may be present in the different sols.

(ii) Several types of silicic acids may be produced during the formation of colloidal acids from the molecularly dispersed acid, these probably have different solubilities.

(iii) Polymerisation of the molecules of the acid may be inhibited at different stages as the kinetics of such reactions are known to be susceptible to many influences. Ultramicrons of various sizes will thus be formed. These have possibly different solubilities. The difference in p_H obtained by previous workers by titration of alkali silicates with strong acids probably arises out of this effect. The crystalloidal solubility of the colloidal particles is practically negligible but the sols may contain different amounts of dissolved silicic acid in equilibrium with the fine micelles of different silicic acids.

(iv) The method used for the determination of dissolved silica may not be sufficiently reliable.

It appears from the investigations of Treadwell and Wieland (*loc.cit.*) and Harman (*loc. cit.*) that sodium silicate is completely converted into silicic acid between p_H 5.0 and p_H 6.0. The sols have p_H values below 5.0 and therefore it is very likely that the sols used in this investigation do not contain any sodium hydrogen silicate as such. The discrepancies between the observed and calculated p_H values (Table XI) indicate that fine micelles have passed through the ultrafilter and these have free hydrogen ions associated with them. More probably it is due to a trace of hydrochloric acid.

Values of K_1 obtained by dividing K_1S by the corresponding values of S are given in Table XII.

TABLE XII.

Sol _s	Silica content per litre.	S (g. mol.).	K_1S .*	K_1 .	Mean K_1 .
Q	0.26 g. mol.	8.3×10^{-4}	4.93×10^{-13}	5.9×10^{10}	
T	0.17	9.8	5.49	5.6	5.2×10^{10}
L'	0.10	6.8	3.28	4.8	
P	0.027	4.7	2.05	4.4	

The values of K_1 given in the above table may be taken to be practically constant if one considers the wide differences in the values of K_1 , the

* From Table X.

first dissociation constant of dissolved silicic acid obtained by previous workers (from 10^{-9} to 10^{-10} , *vide* Table IXA). K_1 , however, decreases from 5.9×10^{-10} to 4.4×10^{-10} as the concentration of silicic acid present in the sol diminishes from 0.26 to 0.027 g. mol per litre. The small variations in the values of K_1 may be attributed to errors of measurements. The mean value 5.2×10^{-10} probably gives the true value for the first dissociation constant of silicic acid.

The difference in p_K , given in Tables IX and that obtained by previous workers by titration of alkali silicates with strong acids arises out of a difference in the mode of reaction of silicic acid sol in the colloidal state. A higher energy appears to be necessary to dissolve the silicic acid molecules from the colloidal particles and the maximum buffering, characteristic of the slope near half neutralisation shifts to a higher p_H and consequently indicates a higher p_K . Calculation of buffer index will consequently be of value in understanding the nature of the interaction.

Buffer Capacity of Silicic Acid Sols.

The buffer capacities ($\Delta B/\Delta p_H$) at different points in the titration curves (*vide* curves 11, 13 and 15) of the sols K, L and L' have been plotted against the equilibrium concentration of added alkali. They have been compared with those of a hypothetical acid, having the same dissociation constant and total acidity as the corresponding sol. The theoretical buffer capacities have been calculated according to the following equation (Slyke, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1922, 22, 525).

$$\beta = 2.303 \frac{a \cdot K \cdot H}{(K + H)^2},$$

where β represents the buffer capacity.

a is the total acidity determined by the stoichiometric concentration of SiO_2 present in the sol.

K is the dissociation constant determined from the p_H at the point of half neutralisation.

H represents the hydrogen ion concentration.

The buffer capacity curves (*vide* curves 11, 13, 15) are smooth and show only one maximum near about the point of half neutralisation. The

presence of only one maximum in the buffer capacity curves indicates that only the first stage of neutralisation has been reached up to the second inflexion point.

The maximum values of the buffer capacities of the sols near about the point of half neutralisation, have been compared with those of the corresponding hypothetical acids. The results are given in Table XIII.

TABLE XIII.

Sol.	SiO ₂ per litre.	Maximum buffer capacity of sol.	Corresponding theoretical value in true solution.
K	0.33 g. mol.	0.54	0.20
L	0.27	0.67	0.15
Q	0.26	0.45	0.14
L	0.10	0.172	0.058
P	0.027	0.035	0.015

Thus the values of the maximum buffer capacities in the titration curves of the sols are considerably greater than those in the theoretical curves. The greater buffer capacity observed in the case of the sols arises from a continuous solution of the colloidal particles, which act as a reservoir from which fresh quantities of acids are generated.

C O N C L U S I O N .

The hydrogen electrode when cleansed and plantinised before each experiment gives fairly reproducible p_H values of silicic acid sols. Silicic acid possesses an intrinsic acid character. Analysis of the ultrafiltrates shows that acids are not present as impurities in quantities to account for the form of the titration curves.

Titration curves of silicic acid sols with different bases show inflexion points at the same concentration of added bases. The buffering action indicated by the slopes of the titration curves, however, indicate that the relative intensities with which the different bases react with the sol are in the order : $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2 > \text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2 > \text{NaOH}$.

Titration curves of silicic acid sols with concentrated alkali show a second inflexion point at a high p_H value. The p_H at the second inflexion diminishes with the concentration of silicic acid in the sol. The total

acidity calculated from this inflexion point shows a fair agreement with the silica content of the sol. The p_K value of the sol calculated at the points of half neutralisation according to Henderson's equation is not in agreement with those found for dissolved silicic acid.

The ultrafiltrates of different sols contain different amounts of silicic acid. These variations have been attributed to the presence of (i) varying amounts of fine micelle and (ii) ultramicrons of various sizes having different solubilities in the different sols.

The values of K_1 , obtained by dividing K_1S , calculated according to the equation

$$K_1S = [H^+] \{ [H^+] + [B^+] - [OH^-] \}$$

by S , the content of dissolved silicic acid estimated in the ultrafiltrate of the sol are of an order similar to that obtained by previous workers from titrations of silicates by acids.

The buffer capacity curve shows only one maximum near about the point of half neutralisation. The maximum value of the buffer capacity is considerably greater than that of the neutralisation curve of a dissolved acid having the same total acidity and dissociation constant as the sol.

The nature of the interaction of silicic acid sols with bases has been discussed.

The author takes this opportunity to offer his thanks to Prof. J. N. Mukherjee, D.Sc., for his suggestions and advice, to the Imperial Council of Agricultural Research, India, under whose employment the author has carried out this work, and to the University of Calcutta for permission to work in the Physical Chemistry Laboratories of the University College of Science and for other facilities.

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Received September 23, 1939.